

What is the investment?

Equipment	Initial Cost
Automated concentrator	€40,000
Manual (non-automated)	€29,000

Annual operational costs

Cleaning and maintenance	~ €300/year
Motor replacement (every 4 years)	~ €100/year
Energy use per m ³ of slurry	Sow slurry: €0.018/m ³ Fattening pig slurry: €0.035/m ³

Further details

- € **Total budget:** € 270.967
- Total financed:** € 83.109,07 (EU); € 110.167,83 (DARF)
- Main funding source:** Rural Development Program 2014-2020 for Operational Groups
- Rural Development Programme:** 2014ES06RDRP009 Spain - Rural Development Programme (Regional) - Catalunya

🕒 Ended, 2015 - 2017

📍 Catalunya, Spain

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Slurry Concentrator

Slurry Concentrator to Reduce Transport Costs and Improve Manure Management

Why implement this innovation on your farm?

Livestock farms often produce more slurry than can be applied on nearby land. This creates the need to transport slurry to more distant fields, a process that is logistically complex and increasingly expensive. The slurry concentrator offers a practical solution by **separating the raw slurry into two phases:**

- A **concentrated phase**, which contains most of the nutrients (especially nitrogen and phosphorus) and is suitable for transport to fields further away.
- A **diluted phase**, mainly water with a lower nutrient content, which can be applied to closer plots.

By reducing the overall volume that needs to be transported, this system helps **lower fuel costs, reduce time spent on logistics, and improve the efficiency of nutrient use.** Both fractions remain in liquid form, so they can still be applied using the **same tanker and tractor** that farmers already use, without the need for new machinery.

Slurry Concentrator

Main benefits

- **Lower transport costs** by reducing slurry volume by 20–30%
- **Better nutrient use efficiency**, with most nitrogen and phosphorus retained in the concentrated fraction
- **Less environmental impact**, especially in Nitrate Vulnerable Zones
- **Compatible with existing machinery** (no need to buy new tankers or tractors)
- **Can be shared** among neighbouring farms or used by cooperatives
- **More flexible manure management**, especially for farms with distant land or limited spreading periods

When do I start saving money?

Savings depend on how much slurry you treat and your farm's average transport distance.

According to real case data (average transport distance = 135 km):

- With sow slurry, you start saving when you treat >350 m³/year
- With fattening pig slurry, you start saving when you treat >500 m³/year

At 1,000 m³/year, annual savings can reach up to €900 — mostly due to reduced transport costs and better nutrient use.

When will I recover my investment?

Equipment Type	Slurry Type	ROI in 5 years	ROI in 10 years
Automated concentrator	Sow slurry	6,298 m ³ /year	3,316 m ³ /year
	Fattening pigs	9,105 m ³ /year	4,795 m ³ /year
Manual concentrator	Sow slurry	4,658 m ³ /year	2,497 m ³ /year
	Fattening pigs	6,734 m ³ /year	3,610 m ³ /year

Practical recommendation:

The larger your farm, the faster the return. The system can also handle both types of slurry without modifications.

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